

The Synthesis of *o*-Aldehydocarboxylic Acids.

BY JOHN H. GARDNER.

In a recent paper, Chakravarti describes as a general method for the synthesis of substituted phthalaldehyde acids, the oxidation of symmetrically substituted naphthalene derivatives to phthalonic acids followed by the decomposition of the latter to the phthalaldehyde acids (Chakravarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 693). As a specific example, he described in detail the preparation of 5-methoxyphthalaldehyde acid from 2:6-dimethoxynaphthalene. Since this work is very close to some investigations which have been carried out in this laboratory, some of which have been published, it was thought desirable to report some of our results at this time. I wish to state explicitly that there is no intention of disputing Chakravarti's priority in demonstrating that this method is of general application.

As a preliminary study, the oxidation of *α*-methoxynaphthalene was studied. While it was expected that the main product would be phthalonic acid, it was hoped that the ring bearing the methoxyl group would be sufficiently resistant to oxidation to permit of the formation of some methoxyphthalonic acid. However, when a solution of the oxidation product was treated with aniline, the aniline condensation product of phthalonic acid was obtained in good yield and purity. Its identity was confirmed by conversion to the aniline derivative of phthalaldehyde acid. There was no evidence of the presence of any methoxyphthalonic acid.

Later, 3:5-dimethoxynaphthalene was oxidised in a similar way with alkaline permanganate. 3-Methoxyphthalonic acid was formed as was shown by its conversion to 3-methoxyphthalaldehyde acid (Naylor and Gardner, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 53, 4109). As this work has already been published elsewhere, it will not be repeated here.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Oxidation of α-methoxynaphthalene.—*α*-Methoxynaphthalene (39.5g.) was suspended in 0.5*N*-sodium hydroxide (500 c. c.). A hot

solution of potassium permanganate (212 g.) in water (1500 c.c.) was added during $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours. The mixture was boiled for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour after the last addition of permanganate. Ethyl alcohol was added to decompose any remaining permanganate. The solution was cooled and filtered. The filtrate was acidified with hydrochloric acid and evaporated to 500 c.c. Aniline (100 c.c.) was added and the mixture was heated on the water-bath for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours. It was then filtered. There was precipitated 39 g. of the aniline derivative of phthalonic acid, m.p. $159-60^\circ$ (decomp.), after crystallisation from alcohol.

Decomposition of the aniline derivative of phthalonic acid.—A suspension of the aniline derivative of phthalonic acid (28 g.) in sodium-dried xylene (190 c.c.) was boiled for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours. After cooling the solid precipitate was filtered out, yield 10 g., m.p. $175-76^\circ$ after crystallisation from alcohol. A mixed melting point with the aniline derivative of phthalaldehyde acid (m.p. $176-77^\circ$) melted at $176-77^\circ$, showing that the materials were identical.

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
WASHINGTON UNIVERSITY,
ST. LOUIS, MISSOURI, U.S.A.

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